

Figure 4, panel B

Manuscript

Calu-3

Lane	Sample	
1	Marker	
2	Calu-3 (Parental)	Trial 01
3	Calu-3 (CTSL-cMYC)	
4	Empty	
5	Marker	
6	Calu-3 (Parental)	Trial 02
7	Calu-3 (CTSL-cMYC)	

File name: Figure 4B_WB_cMYC_HRPO

File name: Figure 4B_WB_cMYC_Brightlight

File name: Figure 4B_WB_ACTB_HRPO

File name: Figure 4B_WB_ACTB_Brightlight

